

THE EFFECT OF PICTURE SERIES IN TEACHING WRITING EXPLANATION TEXT AT SMA DARUSSALAMAH

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Abstract: The focus on find out whether there is an impact on students' ability to write explanatory texts using serial picture media. The respondent of picture series in writing explanation text at SMA Darussalamah for eleventh grade is twenty six respondents. The method is quantitative. The researcher used pre-experimental design. Instruments that used the researcher was pre-test and post-test. In the scoring rubric, the researcher knew that the ideal average value was 44.9 while the ideal standart deviation was 11.91. In addition, their scores in writing were getting better over time. The pre - test's average value was 38.69; and the post-test was 52.08. Additionally, in pre-test, the standart deviation was 10.85. It means that the final results they got was homogenous because the standart deviation is lower than the ideal. Meanwhile, in the post-test, the opposite happened. Their achievement was various because their average score was higher than the ideal average score. Finally, it can be proved that using picture series had an impact on improving students's writing skills.

Keywords: Picture series, writing ability, SMA Darussalamah

Introduction

Language is something that we used for communication with other people. It helps us to express our feelings. Both written and spoken language are used for communication in our daily activities. Language is a term of expressing something that has meaning. [1] Every country in this world has a different language touse and English is agreed to be used by all people over the world to communicating one and each other.

In education, activities for sharing knowledge and experience is called by teaching. It organized for intellectual growth and knowledge. In line with Jeremy's statement that language teaching, reflects the times it takes place in. [2]

Four skills are important to be mastered by the teacher when they teaching English. Those are speaking, writing, listening, and reading. They are grouped into two parts; productive and receptive. The skills that produce languages like speaking and writing belong to a productive group. The other two skills - listening and reading - belong to a receptive group because they are skills which is receive a language. Mastering all skills are very important to improve our English skills because every skill represents many aspects. Writing is crucial for both business and personal life, according to Carter, because it is how others will gauge our level of thinking.[3]

For students, it's not easy for mastering writing skills, especially academic writing. It supported by writing is the maximum hard ability to grasp for 2d or overseas language

learners. [4] Academic writing is a type of writing used at the high school and college levels. [5] The difficulties was found in producing and arranging the ideas, and additionally interpreting the concept into a textual content that can be understood by the reader. The Standard of Competency and Basic Competence of curriculum 2006 of English learning amplifies Richards and Renandya's statement. According to the curriculum, the writing skill is located withinside the ultimate element after different talents due to the fact the scholars ought to practice the whole thing that they've withinside the 3 competencies before. So, this ability can't be discovered at once.[6]

In writing, students must notify the language used, how to arrange a good paragraph, the diction, placement of punctuation, and the most important is the content. Most students underestimate themselves before they start writing. Harmer argues that writing is a complicated skill because it needs more information and appropriate skill to deliver a message. [7] Writing is the final stage after three skills in the process of teaching and learning.[8] Teachers must prepare interesting lessons and choose topics according to the knowledge of their students. [9] In order to provide a learning environment for students, Salam contends that learning material is a unit that is systematically organized in both written and non-written forms. [10]

Anderson and Anderson stated that explanation text is a type of writing that explains how or something happens. [11] The students tell that they did not know the structure of explanation text like generic description and the structure of language. They said that they feel a little bit upset about how to generate those texts. It's because they were only given an example of the text based on their handbook and then the teacher gave instructions to write or generate their text with restricted guidelines. It seems like the class activities monotonous. Students with less grades are a common problem in English subjects. Mostly students with limited class activities don't have enough time to improve their lacking score. The teacher only assigned a substitute task to fix their lacking score. The media used in the classroom also influences students' ability to write an explanation text. Based on the handbook is not enough to stimulate students to make good explanation texts. It was proven by less variety of media that used in the teaching process have not shown maximum results in making explanation text. To facilitate students in writing explanation texts, teaching media or visual aids are provided, as well as charts are one of them that can be applied to students. Mohanty argued that a chart is a diagram consists of facts, and visual symbols to summarize, compare, contrast, and performances which is explain the material easily and interestingly.[12] Based on Hidhayati, Sabat, & Satyawati states pictures have the power to transform pupils' thoughts and imagination from the abstract to the concrete. [13]

Looking at the above problems, the researcher applied picture series as a means to overcome the problems in teaching and learning process. This media is supposed to improve students' ability in writing explanation text. Wright thinks that picture series has two advantages, to help students retell something since they can represent places, objects, and people and to help students understand the general context. [14] So, this media is appropriate to use in teaching writing explanation text.

Although many researchers are studying, so far, this research is different because the researcher investigates how to improve students' ability to write explanatory texts by attracting students' interest through serial pictures and helping students to be more creative by writing down their ideas that appear with the help of existing serial pictures.

This research was conducted because there is not much research on writing explanation text because explanation text is a complicated text. The purpose of conducting this research is to find out whether there is an impact on students' ability to write

explanatory texts using serial picture media. The results of this study will be able to inform teachers that there is an increase in students' ability to write explanation text if the teacher uses serial picture media with serial pictures, students become more creative and find it easier to compose coherent explanation texts.

Methodology

In this study, the researcher used quantitative research. Sugiyono stated Quantitative research can be interpreted as a method based on the Postitivism's philosophy, which is used to examine specific populations or samples. [15] The philosophy of positivism looks at reality or phenomenon, which can be classified as concrete, observed, and measurable. Data collection using research instruments, where data analysis is quantitative. Quantitative research consists of experimental design and non-experimental design. In this study, the author used an experimental design. Where it can produce complete and valid information. There are four types of experimental designs, which can be pre-experimental, true experimental, factorial and quasi-experimental. This study used a pre-experimental design, specifically in the pre- and post-test controls. The purpose of this study is to determine whether there is any significant improvement in the effectiveness of the picture series in teaching essay writing to 11th grade students of SMA Darussalamah.

The study was conducted at SMA Darussalamah. Located at Jerukgamping Krian in Sidoarjo. It has three classes divided into three levels. It includes 96 students. There are five teachers at this school, including one English teacher. The study was conducted at the end of the second semester 2022/2023 school year. The campaign then ran from May 6 to 13, 2023. Study participants were XI students. Class collaborative work by SMA Darussalamah, researcher and English teacher. In eleventh-grade was 26 students.

Pre-test and Post-test

Pre-test is the first instrument that used to collect the data. From this pre-test, the researcher will find out how far the students' ability in mastering the ability to write explanation text. In the test, the researcher asked the students to write an explanation text. The researcher gave them a guidance to make an explanation text in turn, without preparation time. The students should write an explanation text in 20 minutes. The pre-test consists of the name of students/group, attendance number, the title of explanation text that the students asked to do.

Post-test is used to determine whether there are effects that appear after being given the use of picture series treatment in the ability to write an explanation text. The guidance of the post-test is same with the pre-test.

Table 1. The rating scored for writing skill

Criteria of mastery	Level
91-100	Excellent
81-90	Very good
71-80	Good
60-70	Fair
50- 59	Poor
Less than 50	Very poor

Scoring Rubric

This scoring rubric used to giving students score along the observation or treatment was given to the students. This rubric will be held and filled out by researchers and teachers in the class so that the assessment is objective.

Table 2. Scoring Rubric

No.	Name	Content(1-5)	Paragraph Organization(1-5)	Vocabulary (1-5)	Grammar(1-5)	Mechanic (Spelling and Punctuation) (1-5)	Total Score
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Results and Discussion

Based on the data above, there are one class taken in this study. As a start the researcher gave a pre- test to determine students' writing ability. Then the students were given treatment form picture series as the way in teaching explanation text. At the final, the class were given post-test. By giving post-test the researcher will know the effect of giving the treatment by looking at the result of the pre-test and post-test. The result could be seen in the student's achievement in writing skill whether there was improvement in their writing skill or not after used picture series.

This study used pre-experimental design. An English teacher and class XI students of SMA Darussalam participated in this study. It was held from May 6th to May 13th 2023. There were two meetings in a week. The objective of this research study was to find out whether there is an effect on increasing students' writing skills after being given a picture series as a learning medium at SMA Darussalamah.

Table 3. The result of pre-test and post-test

Categories	Frequency	
	Pre-test	Post-test
Excellent	0	0
Very Good	0	0
Good	0	2
Fair	0	4
Poor	7	10
Very Poor	19	10

Based on the table 3, the application of picture series in the process of teaching and learning writing is proven to improve students' writing skills. A description of the fix are:

1. The students' writing ability in five The students' writing skills in five aspects, namely content, organization, vocabulary, language use, and mechanic, after applied picture series has improved. Previously students had difficulty in finding ideas to arrange the explanation text. After they saw picture series, they found an idea for compiling text and stringing it into explanation text according to the ideas that appeared through the pictures. Indirectly, they got guidance on what they should write.

The second problem was regarding the arrangement of the text. By using picture series, they knew how to compose explanation text well because there were pictures of sequential events in it. The next obstacle was the lack of mastery of vocabulary. They knew more new vocabulary through rubric provided in the picture series. When they were given picture series and rubric with vocabulary, they could use the existing vocabulary to construct sentences based on these instructions. When they did not know the meaning of a word available to describe the pictures, they would look it up using their dictionary. So that the picture series can add to the vocabulary they knew. The next problem were punctuation and capitalization. They did not know how to put proper punctuation and capitalization beforehand. But after they did the exercises which given in the first and second treatment, they could use punctuation and capitalization better. So that this could improved their sentence structure is better. Overall, the process of improving children's writing skills through the use of picture sets can be done well.

2. The development of students' writing skills is also supported by the improvement of writing results. In the scoring sheet, the researcher knows that the ideal mean is 44.9 while the ideal standard deviation is 11.91. Additionally, their writing scores improved over time. The mean value of the pretest was 37.69; and the post-test was 52.08. Additionally, during pretesting, the standard deviation was 10.85. This means the final results they get are homogenous because the standard deviation is lower than ideal. Meanwhile, during the post-test, the opposite happened. Their success is uniform because their average score is higher than the ideal average score. Finally, it can be demonstrated that the use of visual sets has an impact on improving students' writing skills.

Summary

Overall, it can be concluded that students' writing ability increased after using the picture set. Thanks to the activities performed previously, the children were able to form and develop their ideas through a series of images provided by the researcher. They can organize the explanatory text into correct sentences because the vocabulary section helps them use the correct words.

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that students' writing skills increased after being given a picture series as a learning medium. The description of these action was:

